

HARNESSING WIND RENEWABLE ENERGY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The research aims to harness wind renewable energy in Nigeria. The monthly mean wind speed of 20 anemometer stations data was acquired from the archives of the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET) in Oshodi, Lagos, Nigeria, covering the years 1951 to 2012. The descriptive statistical method was used in this study to better comprehend data characteristics and variances using mean wind speed statistical and mann-kendall's test and Matlab software. The application aims to detail data behaviors, situations, events, and results from 1951 to 2012 and assess their statistical importance. The coefficients of variations (CV), which range from 19.87% to 50.32%, are large, according to the statistical findings. Higher CV and monthly mean daily wind speeds are typically found in the country's north. According to the findings, the northwestern cities displayed a bimodal maxima that took place in the winter months of December, January, and February as well as in the early summer months of June. The north eastern and north central cities similarly reported the highest wind speeds in March, April, and May. Similarly, the northern region's minima was observed from late summer (August) to mid-autumn (September, October, and November). The cities in the southwest experienced their highest wind speed in the spring (March and April) and summer (July and August). Their minima was recorded in late autumn (November). The south eastern region recorded maxima during spring (March and April) and the minima occurred in late autumn (November). The northern region recorded the best and highest mean wind speed where Kano recorded the maximum wind speed mean of 7.900 m/s and Yelwa having recorded the minima wind speed mean of 3.524 among the northern region. while the western region recorded the poorest mean wind speed of 2.966 m/s by Oshogbo and their highest recorded mean wind speed is 4.635 m/s recorded by Lagos (Ikeja). Hence, Nigeria's northern region is a good place to generate wind power.

KEYWORDS: Harnessing, Wind, Renewable, Energy in Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the country's power needs, we must understand that the world is progressively shifting from non-renewable energy sources to renewable ones. Countries have made the conscious decision to transition from fossil fuel dependence to a sustainable energy system. The key to a future free of carbon emissions is clean electricity. Wind energy is harnessed by employing turbines to transform the kinetic energy of flowing air into electrical power. The wind power channeled to the propeller-like blades around a rotor turns the rotor connected to shaft to rotates a generator to produce power. Wind speed, air density, and the

area swept by the turbine blades all affect a wind turbine's output power (Jungo, 2002). Both onshore (on land) and offshore (offshore) wind renewable energy can be used. These wind farms can produce significant amounts of electricity and are sustainable and efficient. Wind speeds of 10 to 15 km/h (about 3 to 4 m/s) are typically needed for wind turbines to begin producing power, with peak output occurring at 50 to 60 km/h. Turbines turn off when winds reach 90 km/h for safety. Generally, average annual wind speeds of at least 6.5 m/s (14.1 mph) are necessary for economically feasible power generation. The main technique, in which wind energy is captured by blades and used to power a generator that generates electricity by spinning a rotor on a shaft. The most popular type, horizontal-axis turbines, have blades that rotate on a horizontal axis and are usually installed atop tall towers to access quicker, more reliable wind. Turbines that run on a vertical axis are helpful for harnessing wind from various directions and are frequently simpler to maintain.

Literature Review

Review of Related Works

Okoye *et al.* (2020). They researched on Investigation of Wind Energy Resource Potential in Six Nigerian Locations for Power Generation. They found out that the Weibull distribution model has been employed in analyzing a ten year wind data from six chosen locations in Nigeria, three each from northern and southern settlements. Owerri, Portharcourt, and Abeokuta have yearly mean wind speeds of 3.25, 3.27, and 2.76 meters per second, respectively, whereas Sokoto, Bauchi, and Lokoja have mean wind speeds of 4.33, 4.37, and 4.52 meters per second. Sokoto, Bauchi, and Lokoja have annual power densities of 49.14, 59.56, and 69.94 W/m², respectively, while Abeokuta, Owerri, and Port Harcourt have annual power densities of 14.22, 25.77, and 23.76 W/m², respectively. As a result, while wind resources in the majority of southern Nigeria are only appropriate for water pumping applications, wind resources in the majority of northern Nigeria are acceptable for medium-scale electric power generation.

Ayoade *et al.* (2012). They researched on Wind Energy Potential in Nigeria. They found out that Nigeria has the capacity to harness wind energy due to the fact that some locations especially in the northern region has annual wind speed of of 10–15 km/h (about 3–4 m/s) to start generating electricity.

Abiodun I. C., & Anisiji O. E. (2024). They researched on Statistical Analysis and Estimation of Wind Speed Characteristics and Energy Potential for Power Generation in Forcados, South Southern, Nigeria. This study looks at Forcados, Nigeria's wind speed characteristics and wind energy generation potential. Between 2009 and 2019, wind speed measurements at 10 and 50 m altitudes obtained from the Nigeria Meteorology Agency in Lagos were examined. The wind energy potential was assessed using the Weibull distribution function. According to the findings, wind energy harvesting potential was best during the mid-wet season (July and August) and lowest toward the start of the dry season (December). High values for the Weibull shape and scale parameters were found when the wind speed characteristics were examined in order to determine the wind energy potential. These results show that favorable wind speeds are available and that Forcados is always breezy. Additionally, the average monthly and annual wind speeds were higher than the 3.0- to 4.0-m/s minimum needed for the majority of wind turbines to function. Forcados is a good place to generate wind power because of the wind profile and its characteristics establish Forcados and the neighboring surroundings have a great deal of potential for producing wind power.

Mu'azu M. B., Oricha J. Y., Boyi J. (2009). They researched on Renewable Energy Resource in Nigeria: An Estimation of Wind Power Potentials. Using average wind speed data from Nigerian meteorological centers and satellite-derived meteorology and solar energy parameters from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), they discovered the daily average wind speed (vd, m/s) for 130 sections (1° x 1° of latitude and longitude), or 2°E – 15°E longitudes and 4°N – 14°N latitudes, enclosing Nigeria. The average wind power potential in Nigeria was calculated by using the data to show the isovents at a height of 50 meters.

Wind Speed Requirement

An average annual wind speed of at least 6.5 m/s (14.1 mph) is usually required for economically viable power generation. Wind turbines typically require wind speeds of 10 to 15 km/h (about 3 to 4 m/s) to begin generating electricity, reaching peak output around 50 to 60 km/h in order to ensure safety. The Key Wind Speed Benchmarks for electricity generation are as follows:

- (i) Cut-in Speed (Start-up): 8–14 km/h (2–4 m/s).
- (ii) Rated Speed (Max Output): 36–60 km/h (10–15 m/s).
- (iii) Cut-out Speed (Shutdown): 90 km/h (25 m/s).

Utility-scale turbines need greater wind speeds, ideally in areas with an average yearly wind speed of more than 5.8 m/s, whereas small turbines begin producing power at lower rates, about 2 m/s. Since wind speed and power are related, doubling the speed results in an eight-fold increase in power. Open plains, water, and mountain gaps with steady winds are the best places to absorb wind and maximize generation. Wind characteristics are as follows:

- (i) Wind Velocity / Air Speed: Refers to the speed of the wind.
- (ii) Wind Strength / Wind Intensity: Refers to the force of the wind.
- (iii) Wind Power Density / Wind Energy Potential: Refers to the energy available at a given location.
- (iv) Cut-in/Cut-out Velocity: Technical terms for start and stop speeds.

Methodology

Descriptive Statistical Method

The method applied in this research is descriptive Statistical method, applied for data collection and used to understand it's characteristics and variations. The application of this descriptive approach is aimed at detailing data behaviors, situations, events, and outcomes with Statistical Method applied to understand the mean wind speed across a period of 1951-2012. Matlab software will also be used for the mean wind speed simulation in order to verify the wind speed variations across different months in the country.

Monthly Mean Wind Speed Data

Table 3.1 displays monthly mean wind speed of 20 anemometer stations spread across Nigeria and obtained from the archives of the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET) Oshodi, Lagos Nigeria. The data covers a period of 1951 - 2012.

Table 3.1: Nigerian Monthly Mean Wind Speed Data Of 20 Anemometer Stations

S/N	Station	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Altitude (m)	Period	Sequence Lenth (Months)	Missing Data (%)
1	Benin city	6.19	5.36	77.80	1967-2012	552	0
2	Calabar	4.58	8.21	62	1961-2012	624	0
3	Enugu	6.28	7.34	142	1961-2012	624	5.77
4	Ibadan	7.22	3.58	234	1961-2012	624	9.62
5	Ilorin	8.26	4.30	308	1961-2012	624	5.77
6	Port Harcourt	5.01	6.57	18	1960-2012	636	0
7	Wari	5.31	5.44	600	1967-2012	552	30.43
8	Lagos (Ikeja)	6.34	3.20	40	1951-2012	744	0
9	Oshogbo	7.46	4.29	305	1961-2012	624	11.54
10	Yola	9.16	12.26	191	1963-2012	600	2
11	Lokoja	7.43	6.44	113	1964-2012	588	2.04
12	Owerri	5.25	7.13	91	1977-2012	432	0
13	Ogoja	6.40	8.48	117	1978-2012	420	17.14
14	Makurdi	7.42	8.37	113	1961-2012	624	13.46
15	Maiduguri	11.51	13.05	354	1961-2012	624	9.62
16	Bauchi	10.17	9.48	591	1961-2012	624	21.15
17	Kano	12.05	8.32	476	1961-2012	624	7.69
18	Sokoto	12.55	5.12	351	1968-2012	552	2.17
19	Yelwa	10.53	4.45	244	1962-2012	612	11.78
20	Kaduna (Zaria)	10.42	7.19	645	1967-2012	564	10.64

Analytical Estimation of wind characteristics

After closely examining the monthly data, some missing entries were found, as indicated in table 3.1 above. The number of stations with missing records varied from 2% to roughly 10%, with only 5 stations having no missing observations. Data from stations with missing records of no more than 5% should be used, according to (Shongwe et al. 2006). However, achieving this can be extremely difficult, particularly in areas with limited data, like this one. In order to accommodate the missing data in this study, (Ngongondo et al. 2011) utilized a more accommodating 10% maximum threshold that was suggested by (Hosking & Wallis, 1997). According to (Helsel & Hirsch, 1992) in the National Nonpoint Source Monitoring Programme (NNSMP, 2011), if the data gap is less than one-third of the entire record, monotonic trend analysis may be used. This research follows this advice, which is predicated on the use of non-parametric tests that are resilient to significant data gaps.

Statistical Analysis of the Data

To test for homogeneity, the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis (K-W) test was used. When the climatic series of observations is homogeneous, there are no jumps—abrupt, non-climatological peaks or decreases. The SPSS software was used to assess the distribution's descriptive statistics. Although the Mann-Kendall tests are capable of detecting wind Characteristics, they are unable to assess the size of those traits. A linear regression model

was used to quantify the magnitude of the wind characteristics. MATLAB was used to achieve regression analysis and used to generate the bar charts to indicate the seasonal variations of the wind speed data of the stations.

Result and Discussion

Mean Wind Speed Statistical and Mann-Kendall's test results

Table 4.1 displays the stations' wind speed characteristics. The majority of the stations have large coefficients of variation (CV), indicating significant national variability in wind speed. A quick glance at the table shows that neither the mean nor the CV exhibit any obvious distributional patterns.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Wind

N/S	Stations	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	Range	C.V %
1	Benin city	552	1.1	8.2	3.481	0.9266	7.1	26.62
2	Calabar	624	0.0	8.3	3.871	1.1474	8.3	29.64
3	Enugu	588	0.0	11.0	5.282	1.4183	11.0	26.85
4	Ibadan	5.64	0.2	8.6	4.060	1.2619	8.4	31.08
5	Ilorin	588	1.0	8.6	4.411	1.4821	7.6	33.6
6	Port Harcourt	636	0.0	7.0	3.633	0.9971	7.0	27.45
7	Wari	384	0.5	6.8	3.321	0.6419	6.3	19.87
8	Lagos (Ikeja)	744	0.3	10.5	4.635	1.6960	10.2	36.59
9	Oshogbo	552	0.0	5.6	2.966	1.1026	5.6	37.18
10	Yola	588	0.5	11.0	3.993	2.0091	10.5	50.32
11	Lokoja	576	0.3	6.2	3.063	1.0555	5.9	34.46
12	Owerri	432	1.8	8.1	3.455	0.7840	6.3	22.69
13	Ogoja	348	1.2	9.8	3.633	1.1195	8.6	30.81
14	Makurdi	540	1.3	9.2	4.781	1.4973	7.9	31.32
15	Maiduguri	564	1.2	9.1	5.227	2.2814	10.9	49.37
16	Bauchi	492	0.0	10.9	4.621	1.6468	7.9	31.51
17	Kano	576	2.0	15.0	7.900	2.4256	13.0	30.7
18	Sokoto	540	2.4	12.9	7.471	1.9474	10.5	26.07
19	Yelwa	540	0.0	8.0	3.524	1.4164	8.0	40.19
20	Kaduna (Zaria)	504	2.4	10.9	5.285	1.4716	8.5	27.84

With remarkable mean wind speeds of 7.471 m/s and 7.9 m/s, respectively, Sokoto and Kano in the North West are shown in Table 4.1 as the windiest stations. The Yola and Bauchi north-east stations have exceptional CVs of 50.32% and 49.37%, respectively. The southwestern cities of Oshogbo (2.966 m/s), Benin (3.481 m/s), Warri (3.23 m/s), and the north central city of Lokoja (3.063 m/s) have comparatively low monthly mean wind speed data. There are several possible reasons for the variance in wind speed across the stations, as shown in table 4.1. These include topography, orographic, and orogenic factors. Significant effects are also produced by changes in the height and location of anemometers, the roughness of the environment around the stations, and atmospheric forcing (atmospheric

circulation). Compared to stations near forests, hills, mountains, and other intervening structures like tall buildings, wind speeds are typically higher at well-exposed locations. This outcome is expected because the south is characterized by mangroves, swamp forests, tropical rainforests, and tall grasses of the guinea savanna, whereas the north belongs to the dry and semi-arid ecotypes. The results of the Mann-Kendall's test, the individual stations' Kendall's tau b (coefficients of the temporal trends), and the test statistics' p values are displayed in Table 4.2. Additionally shown are the time trend coefficients' statistical significance levels.

Table 4.2: Mann-Kendall's test results and estimates of wind speed magnitudes of the wind speed.

N/S	Stations	Kendall's tau b	P Value	m/s per Month	m/s per Year	m/s per Decade
1	Benin city	-0.097**	0.001	0.0001	0.0012	0.012
2	Calabar	0.317**	0.00	0.0022	0.0264	0.264
3	Enugu	0.193**	0.00	0.0011	0.0132	0.132
4	Ibadan	-0.043**	0.134	0.0028	0.0336	0.336
5	Ilorin	0.295**	0.000	0.0018	0.0216	0.216
6	Port Harcourt	-0.271**	0.000	0.0015	0.018	0.18
7	Wari	0.0003**	0.926	0.0003	0.0036	0.036
8	Lagos (Ikeja)	0.121**	0.000	0.0002	0.0024	0.024
9	Oshogbo	-0.162**	0.000	0.005	0.06	0.6
10	Yola	-0.438**	0.000	0.0058	0.0696	0.696
11	Lokoja	-0.209**	0.000	0.0001	0.012	0.12
12	Owerri	0.025**	0.443	0.00039	0.00468	0.0468
13	Ogoja	-0.052**	0.153	0.00042	0.00504	0.0504
14	Makurdi	0.259**	0.000	0.0018	0.0216	0.216
15	Maiduguri	0.178**	0.000	0.0014	0.0168	0.168
16	Bauchi	-0.382	0.000	0.0009	0.0108	0.108
17	Kano	0.354**	0.000	0.0048	0.0576	0.576
18	Sokoto	-0.094**	0.001	0.0012	0.0144	0.144
19	Yelwa	-0.040**	0.175	0.0013	0.0156	0.156
20	Kaduna (Zaria)	-0.095**	0.002	0.002	0.024	0.24

The estimated wind variation magnitudes in m/s per month, m/s per year, and m/s per decade are displayed in Table 4.2. The deterioration across the periods under consideration is represented by the fluctuations in the wind speed time series. Eight stations (representing 40% of the stations) exhibit a significant wind speed decline at the 1% level, out of the 11 stations (representing 55%) that exhibit downward wind speed fluctuation. These include Benin, Lokoja, Yola, Oshogbo, Bauchi, Sokoto, Kaduna, and Port Harcourt. Seven sites (representing 35%) exhibit considerable upward wind speed at the 1% level, whereas nine stations (representing 45%) exhibit upward wind speed fluctuation. These include Makurdi, Enugu, Calabar, Ilorin, Ikeja, Maiduguri, and Kano. Yelwa, Ibadan, and Ogoja have non-significant downward wind speeds, whereas Owerri and Warri exhibit negligible rising wind speeds.

Mean Wind Speed Simulation Result

The seasonal variations of monthly mean wind speed are presented in Bar charts in Figs 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Fig. 4.1: Northern Regional Monthly Mean Wind Speed

According to the findings, there is a bimodal maxima for the northwestern cities of Yelwa, Kaduna, Sokoto, and Kano. These take place in early summer (June) and winter (December, January, and February). The wind calmest times of year in this area are from late summer (August) to mid-autumn (October). In this case, Yelwa station is unique in that the wind speed peaks in mid-spring (April) and early summer (June) and troughs in late autumn (November). The mid-spring (April) maxima and fall (September, October, and November) minima are recorded for the northeastern cities of Yola, Maidugiri, and Bauchi. However, Maidugiri records its maxima in early spring (March) and early summer (June), which is a tiny departure from this norm.

Fig. 4.2: North Central and South West Regional Monthly Mean Wind Speed

Like the north eastern zone, the north central cities (Lokoja, Ilorin, and Makurdi) experience their windiest season in the spring (March, April, and May) and their wind calmest season in the fall (September, October, and November). Double maxima are seen in the spring (March and April) and summer (July and August). In the southwestern cities of Ibadan, Oshogbo, and Ikeja. Late autumn (November) is when they recorded their lowest wind spread.

Fig. 4.3: South East Regional Monthly Mean Wind Speed

The south-eastern cities of Enugu, Owerri, and Ogoja recorded springtime wind maxima (March and April) and late autumn minima (November). Wind maxima are recorded in the spring (March & April) and late summer (August) for the major southern towns of Benin, Port Harcourt, Warri, and Calabar. Late autumn (November) is when the periods of high wind speed occur. It is evident from the above that while the autumn (specifically November) dominates the periods of high wind speed across Nigeria, the spring (usually March and April) dominates the times of high wind speed.

Discussion of Results

According to the statistical findings, the coefficients of variations (CV), which range from 19.87% to 50.32%, are large. Higher CV and monthly mean daily wind speeds are typically found in the country's north. Then, the northwestern cities displayed a bimodal maxima that took place in the winter months of December, January, and February as well as in the early summer months of June. The north eastern and north central cities similarly reported the highest wind speeds in March, April, and May. Similarly, the northern region's minima was observed from late summer (August) to mid-autumn (September, October, and November). The cities in the southwest experienced their highest wind speed in the spring (March and April) and summer (July and August). Their minima was recorded in late autumn (November). The south eastern region recorded maxima during spring (March and April) and the minima occurred in late autumn (November). The northern region recorded the best and highest mean wind speed where Kano recorded the maximum wind speed mean of 7.900 m/s and Yelwa having recorded the minima wind speed mean of 3.524 among the northern region. while the weatern region recorded the poorest mean wind speed of 2.966 m/s by Oshogbo and their highest recorded mean wind speed is 4.635 m/s recorded by Lagos (Ikeja).

Conclusion

The northern region recorded the best and highest mean wind speed where Kano recorded the maximum wind speed mean of 7.900 m/s and Yelwa having recorded the minima wind speed mean of 3.524 among the northern region. while the weatern region recorded the poorest mean wind speed of 2.966 m/s by Oshogbo and their highest recorded mean wind speed is 4.635 m/s recorded by Lagos (Ikeja). Hence, Nigeria's northern region is a good place to generate wind power.

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